
INNOVATIVE DESIGN: EXPLORING ARCH-CORRUGATED CORES FOR LIGHTWEIGHT AND VERSATILE MODULAR SANDWICH PANELS

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CODE: BCCM7-41

Keywords: Sandwich panel, Corrugated core, 3D printing

Abstract: Modular structures refer to a design approach that subdivides a system into smaller modules or skids, which can be independently created and utilized in different systems. These modules are distinguished by their functional partitioning and well-defined interfaces, making them an efficient and cost-effective construction method. In the realm of engineering, sandwich panels are constructed using stiff skins and a lightweight core, resulting in structures that are lightweight, rigid, and durable. These panels find applications in a wide range of engineering fields. When the core material is designed with a corrugated geometry, it offers several benefits, such as facilitating the passage of electrical conductors and pipes. This is advantageous for the construction and transportation industries, as well as for providing thermal and acoustic insulation. This study introduces an innovative framework that combines modular and sandwich designs, utilizing arch-corrugated cores. The facing and core materials are created through 3D printing using PLA (polylactic acid) and are evaluated through three-point bending tests. The arched core is investigated through six distinct arrangement configurations. The 3D printed prototypes demonstrate promising potential for modular sandwich panels, as they can adapt to different applications. This research unlocks thrilling opportunities for the future advancement and integration of modular sandwich panels in various industries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advances in polymer science and engineering have led the scientific community to focus on the use of sustainable materials as a way to reduce the environmental impact of conventional materials. Biopolymers emerge as a promising solution, being non-polluting, chemically versatile, sustainable, biodegradable, and presenting a wide potential for application in various fields, including the biomedical, textile, and electronics industries, among others [1].

In the same sustainability context, sandwich structural composites have been highlighted both in the academic realm and in the industry at large due to their characteristics of lightweight and efficient structures [2]. Generally, a sandwich panel consists of two high-strength faces and a low-density core. Different materials, such as foams, aramids, aluminium alloys, wood, and polymers, have been used in the fabrication of the core of sandwich panels [3–5]. The choice of core and face material is influenced by the specific application of these structures, their load-bearing lifespan, availability, and cost [3]. Recently, 3D printing technology has been explored to produce panels with remarkable mechanical properties and a variety of patterns, with several studies conducted to investigate the characteristics and behaviour of printed sandwich panels [6–9]. In addition to materials, different core geometries have been investigated, with notable examples including the Honeycomb, featuring cells oriented perpendicular to the faces, and the corrugated core, which has cells oriented in the same direction as the faces.

In [7], the mechanical behaviour of sandwich panels composed of Honeycomb cores and faces manufactured by a 3D printer was investigated. Two types of sandwich structures were fabricated. In the first type, both the core and the outer layers were made of polylactic acid (PLA). In the second type, the outer layers were made of acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) polymer, while PLA was used for the core material. Experimental results showed that the structures exhibited distinct mechanical behaviour under bending load. The sandwich panels with outer layers and core made of PLA demonstrated significant bending properties compared to the other sample. On the other hand, [10] proposed a panel with bidirectional sinusoidal corrugated core. The study investigated the influence of the number of waves on the bending properties of panels with bidirectional or regular corrugated cores. The pattern of each corrugated core consists of a cosine curve with a certain period and amplitude. In the study [11], the effect of printed hierarchical-sinusoidal corrugated core patterns and loading direction on the bending properties of cotton/epoxy composite sandwich panels was investigated. For the cores, six sinusoidal corrugated structures were considered, and manufactured using a 3D printer and polylactic acid material. Additionally, possible arrangements (transverse or longitudinal waves, downward or upward arc) of the sinusoidal corrugated cores concerning the loading direction were considered. It was observed that, for the transverse arrangement, the bending strength of the sandwich panels is significantly improved by changing the core pattern from simple to hierarchical patterns.

It was observed in the published articles that corrugated cores are permanently bonded to the faces using adhesives. Therefore, considering the significant need to develop sustainable non-polluting materials, the aim was to develop a sandwich panel consisting of PLA faces and core through additive manufacturing via 3D printing. The corrugated core is formed by arches and reversibly fits into the faces, meaning the panel can be assembled and disassembled multiple times. This characteristic allows the panel to be adjusted to better suit each application. Different patterns were then considered for the corrugated cores. The effect of core arrangement and loading direction on bending properties was investigated.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Materials

The sandwich panel components are made from 1.75 mm diameter PLA filament, a biobased thermoplastic polymer supplied by 3D LAB – Brazil. The properties of the PLA material can be found in Table 1. Samples are manufactured using a Creality Ender-3 3D printer.

Table 1. Mechanical properties of printed PLA. Available at [12].

Properties	Values
Density [g/cm ³]	1.20
Yield strength [MPa]	24.80
Ultimate tensile strength [MPa]	46.0
Elastic modulus [GPa]	1.90
Elongation [%]	3.69

2.2. Sandwich Panel Design

The core geometry is designed with arched corrugation, incorporating two types of arches with different fittings as well as a semi-arch. The geometric characteristics of the facing and core materials are illustrated in Fig. 1. Six different core arrangements considering (i) the downward or upward disposition of the arches, (ii) alternating or similar patterns and (iii) with or without semi-arches, are established and encoded (Fig. 2).

Figure 1. Details of the geometric properties of the components. Dimensions in millimetres.

Figure 2. Studied core configurations.

The components of the sandwich panels are modelled in SolidWorks software, and then the cores and faces are printed using Creality software and an FDM Ender 3 printer. Initially, a panel composed of six equal arcs arranged alternately is manufactured using the FDM method. The printing parameters included a nozzle temperature of 200°C and a bed temperature of 60°C, as recommended by the manufacturer. The dimensions of the outer layers are set at 75×200 mm² by ASTM C393 [13] standard, and the panel has a thickness of 26.7 mm. A preliminary test revealed that using equal arcs with filled ends through an insert led to unsatisfactory behaviour as they quickly came apart. To ensure the uniformity of the arcs, the decision was made to reinforce them by using complete fittings for greater stability at the junction (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Type of end-fitting: (a) with insert and (b) without insert (full attachment).

2.3. Panel Testing

To assess the mechanical properties of the sandwich panels, specimens undergo flexural testing (Fig. 4). The samples are tested under three-point bending conditions with displacement control, in line with the specifications outlined in ASTM C393 [13] standard. The load-deflection curve of the prepared samples is recorded using an Instron EMIC 23-100 testing machine. Following ASTM C393 [13] standard requirements, the test is carried out at a crosshead speed of 8 mm/min to ensure failure occurs between 3 and 6 minutes. Additionally, a 1 kN load cell is utilized to record the applied load. Three specimens are manufactured and tested for each configuration.

Figure 4. Three-point bending test.

The ultimate shear strength of the core and the bending stress on the faces of the sandwich panels under bending are determined. The ultimate shear strength of the core in a sandwich structure is calculated according to Eq. (1) [13].

$$F_s^{ult} = \frac{P_{max}}{(d + c)b} \quad (1)$$

Here P_{max} represents the maximum force on the force-deflection curve, d denotes the panel thickness, c represents the core thickness, and b indicates the panel width. Furthermore, the bending stress on the face is calculated using Eq. (2) [13].

$$\sigma = \frac{P_{max}S}{2t(d + c)b} \tag{2}$$

Here, S denotes the support span, and t represents the thickness of the sandwich panel face. The values of the geometric properties used in Eqs. (1) and (2) are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Geometric dimensions of the panels used.

Parameter	Values [mm]
d	26.7
c	22.7
b	75.0
S	150.0
t	2.0

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Load-Deflection Curves

Figure 5 illustrates the typical load versus deflection curves of the sandwich panels. It is evident that the panel composed of the corrugated core (6.6.) made with arcs arranged upwards, including semi-arcs, achieves the highest maximum supported load. Furthermore, it is observed that the panels withstand more load when the arcs are turned upwards, as seen in configurations 2.2, 4.4, and 6.6.

Figure 5. Results of the three-point bending tests.

Panels 2.2 and 3.3 experience significant deformation, leading to slipping on the support during the test without rupture occurring (Fig. 6). Three conditions were established as criteria for panel failure and test termination: panel fracture, disengagement of any arch, or exceeding the maximum test time (6 min) without rupture.

Figure 6. Example of excessive deformation and slipping of panel 2.2.

3.2. Mechanical Properties

Table 3 displays the mean maximum loads for each configuration and the evaluated mechanical properties. Except for panels 1.1 and 4.4, the standard deviation values indicate a moderate dispersion, suggesting that the manufacturing process has been satisfactorily executed, maintaining uniformity among the replicates.

Table 3. Mean of the results obtained for the panels.

Panel	P_{med} [N]	F_s^{ult} [kPa]	σ [kPa]
1.1	73.25±9.80	20.20	741.36
2.2	92.56±3.35	25.50	937.68
3.3	38.56±3.07	10.41	390.25
4.4	72.21±10.41	19.50	731.08
5.5	54.65±0.69	15.47	553.14
6.6	119.60±2.33	32.28	1210.56

4. CONCLUSIONS

The proposed modular sandwich panel has demonstrated a versatile design, resulting in impressive mechanical performance. The utilization of the arched corrugated core has led to higher bending deformation, meeting the mechanical requirements for protection and energy absorption in various engineering applications. In conclusion, this study highlights the significant impact of the arrangement of the arcs on the properties of the panel. Placing the arcs upwards provides better support for bending efforts compared to a downward position. Additionally, the use of semi-arcs at the panel ends positively contributes to supporting the efforts. By altering the core pattern, the ultimate shear strength of the core and the bending stress of the faces are significantly increased. Finally, it is recommended to investigate the behaviour of impact energy absorption, as well as the thermal and acoustic properties of these versatile modular sandwich panels.

4.1. Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

4.2. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Flávio Amaral for assisting in the process of the experimental results. Additionally, the authors would like to express their gratitude to the Centre for Innovation and Technology in Composite Materials (UFSJ) and to CNPq (PQ #05553/2023-2).

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